

Protocol

AI-Driven Food Fraud Detection Systems: A Critical Systematic Review of the Detection–Prevention Gap

Authors

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1. Background

Food fraud represents a major challenge for food authenticity, consumer protection, and regulatory oversight. Increasingly sophisticated adulteration practices have stimulated the development of analytical methods integrating artificial intelligence (AI), machine learning (ML), deep learning (DL), spectroscopy, hyperspectral imaging, electronic noses, chromatography, and related technologies.

Although numerous studies report extremely high classification accuracies under laboratory conditions, evidence regarding industrial deployment, external validation, inter-laboratory reproducibility, and contribution to fraud prevention remains limited. Consequently, a potential gap exists between analytical detection capability and real-world prevention effectiveness.

This systematic review aims to evaluate the current state of AI-assisted food fraud detection technologies and to characterize the factors that limit their translation into practical prevention systems.

2. Objectives

Primary Objective

To evaluate the contribution of artificial intelligence-assisted analytical technologies to food fraud prevention and identify factors limiting translation from laboratory detection to operational implementation.

Secondary Objectives

1. To characterize the instrumental technologies used for food fraud detection.
2. To identify the most frequently employed AI architectures and machine-learning algorithms.
3. To quantify the frequency and rigor of external validation procedures.

4. To assess evidence of industrial implementation and regulatory integration.
5. To compare reported performance between classical machine-learning and deep-learning approaches.
6. To evaluate methodological quality and risk of bias of the included studies.

3. Research Questions

RQ1. What is the current state of external validation in AI-based food fraud detection research?

RQ2. What evidence exists regarding industrial implementation and operational deployment?

RQ3. What factors explain the gap between laboratory detection performance and real-world prevention effectiveness?

RQ4. Do deep-learning models outperform classical machine-learning approaches in reported analytical performance?

4. Eligibility Criteria

Inclusion Criteria

Studies will be included when they:

1. Report at least one quantitative performance metric (accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, AUC, R^2 , RMSE, sensitivity, specificity, or equivalent).
2. Apply artificial intelligence, machine learning, deep learning, or chemometric algorithms.
3. Address food fraud, food authentication, adulteration detection, food substitution, origin verification, or related authenticity problems.
4. Describe the analytical or instrumental platform used for data acquisition.
5. Are published in peer-reviewed journals.
6. Were published between January 2021 and June 2026.
7. Are available in English.

Exclusion Criteria

Studies will be excluded when they:

1. Focus exclusively on food safety issues unrelated to fraud.
2. Are conference abstracts lacking methodological detail.
3. Lack quantitative performance metrics.
4. Do not employ AI-based analytical models.
5. Are duplicate publications.
6. Do not provide sufficient methodological information for extraction.

5. Information Sources

The following databases will be searched:

- Scopus
- ScienceDirect
- PubMed
- IEEE Xplore
- MDPI Publisher Platform

Additional manual searches may be performed through reference lists of eligible studies.

6. Search Strategy

General search expression:

(“electronic nose” OR “electronic tongue” OR spectroscopy OR “hyperspectral imaging”) AND (“artificial intelligence” OR “machine learning”) AND (“food fraud” OR adulteration)

Specific search expression:

((“food fraud” OR “food adulteration” OR “food authentication” OR “adulteration detection”) AND (“machine learning” OR “deep learning” OR “artificial intelligence” OR “neural network” OR chemometrics OR “support vector machine” OR “random forest” OR “convolutional neural network”) AND (NIR OR “near-infrared” OR “electronic nose” OR hyperspectral OR spectroscopy OR “gas chromatography” OR Raman OR FTIR))

7. Study Selection

Study selection will follow PRISMA 2020 recommendations.

Titles and abstracts will be screened first.

Potentially eligible records will undergo full-text evaluation.

Disagreements between reviewers will be resolved through discussion and consensus.

A PRISMA flow diagram will document the selection process.

8. Data Extraction

Data will be extracted using a structured seven-domain framework.

Sheet 1 – Study Information

- Authors
- Year
- Journal
- Country
- Food matrix
- Fraud type
- Sample size
- Funding source

Sheet 2 – Instrumental Technology

- Sensor type
- Instrument
- Target compounds
- Sample preparation
- Pre-processing
- Measurement conditions

Sheet 3 – AI Models

- Algorithm category
- Specific model
- Input variables
- Output variables
- Training strategy
- Cross-validation
- External validation

Sheet 4 – Performance Metrics

- Accuracy
- Precision

- Recall
- F1-score
- AUC
- R^2
- RMSE
- Sensitivity
- Specificity

Sheet 5 – Industrial Validation

- Pilot-scale testing
- Industrial environment testing
- Inter-laboratory validation
- Technology readiness level
- Industrial partners

Sheet 6 – Implementation Evidence

- Regulatory integration
- Routine monitoring
- Adoption barriers
- Economic constraints
- Scalability

Sheet 7 – Methodological Quality

- Sample size adequacy
- Dataset diversity
- Preprocessing transparency
- Validation robustness
- Risk of bias
- Overall quality score

9. Risk of Bias Assessment

Methodological quality will be assessed using a structured five-point framework.

The following domains will be evaluated:

1. Sample size adequacy.
2. Dataset diversity.
3. Preprocessing transparency.
4. Validation robustness.
5. Risk of bias.

Studies will be classified as:

- Low risk of bias
- Moderate risk of bias
- High risk of bias

Overall quality scores will range from 1 to 5.

10. Statistical Analysis

The following analyses are planned:

1. Descriptive synthesis of all eligible studies.
2. Comparison of classification accuracy between classical machine-learning and deep-learning approaches using the Mann–Whitney U test.
3. Association between reported accuracy and validation rigor using Fisher’s exact test.
4. Correlation between reported accuracy and methodological quality score using Spearman’s rank correlation coefficient.
5. Frequency analysis of industrial implementation and validation practices.

All analyses will be conducted using a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$.

11. Reporting

The review will be conducted and reported according to the PRISMA 2020 Statement.

12. Protocol Status

This protocol was prepared before final synthesis and reporting of results and is deposited as a permanent public record to ensure methodological transparency and reproducibility.

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